

Initiation rites as a possible key to the decipherment of the *rongorongo* script of Easter Island

M. de Laat

Introduction

The *rongorongo* script of Easter Island has only barely survived the ravages of history. Of the 25 inscribed wooden artefacts in existence – mostly tablets – the majority is badly damaged and only partly legible. Barthel (1958) has published 24 of these texts labelling them alphabetically as A, B, C, etc. His transcriptions and nomenclature will be used in this paper. In addition to this collection, there exists a substantial corpus of very brief texts and isolated signs that have not yet been systematically catalogued. They have been engraved on rock panels, wooden statues, and skulls, painted on *tapa* cloth figures, and tattooed on human skin. When in the second half of the 19th century *rongorongo* came to the attention of the outside world, those with more than a superficial acquaintance with the writing system had all perished. Consequently, the information that has been handed down about the nature of the script, its function in pre-missionary society, and the contents of its inscriptions, is fragmentary and unreliable. Only two things seem reasonably certain: the script was used to record the native tongue – known today as Rapanui – and it was read from left to right in reverse boustrophedon style. Given the correspondence between the number of syllables of the language and the inventory of signs that make up most of the corpus, several researchers have proposed that the script is basically syllabic (e.g., Macri 1996; Pozdniakov 1996; Horley 2005).

There have been only two generally accepted proposals regarding the subject matter of the inscriptions. One structured sequence in text G has been identified as a genealogy (Butinov and Knorozov 1957: 15) and another in text C as a lunar calendar (Barthel 1958: 242-247). These structural analyses, however, have not lead to further breakthroughs. This means that today the semantic or phonetic value of not a single *rongorongo* glyph is known with some degree of certainty.

This study proposes a threefold approach to establish the meaning of a number of signs. The first follows from the notions that several glyphs of the script are figurative and that in other scripts the phonetic value of a sign often derives from (part of) the name of the represented object. Secondly, there is a number of *rongorongo* signs that appear in the petroglyphic record side by side with other figures. The most interesting of these are the glyphs which occur in sites where information on the context of the rock art is available from traditions. A third avenue of research has been opened by Easter Islanders who have – consciously or unconsciously – associated the *rongorongo* script with initiation rites involving young children. A substantial but largely neglected corpus of chants about these initiates provides the material for an examination whether such a connection existed and whether it constitutes a possible point of entry into the seemingly closed system of the Easter Island script.

Easter Island initiation rites

In most pre-modern societies, the coming of age of children was marked by elaborate rites of passage. As female menstruation was particularly feared as a potential source of contamination by supernatural influences, young girls were often isolated from society at the onset of menarche (cf. Frazer 1913: 22-100). In Polynesia where plumpness and fairness were important physical desiderata (especially among high status groups), this quarantine could also involve an avoidance of sunlight to bleach the skin and a special diet combined with a lack of exercise to fatten the body (Buck 1938: 117; Oliver 2002: 127).

Although much of the information on traditional initiation practices was lost during the catastrophic population decline and the comprehensive cultural transformation of Easter Island in the second half of the 19th century, enough details have survived to establish that they conformed to the general scheme of Polynesian custom. Apparently, children from both sexes were secluded in special houses or remote caves for a certain period of time. During this isolation their physical appearance was modified, allegedly in order to become “beautiful”. After this period, the initiates were reintroduced into society with elaborate ceremony.

Although ethnological reports make mention of three different initiation rituals, the descriptions overlap in so many details that either these rites were confused by the informants or they have in fact been closely related. The general term for the seclusion was *huru* (Brown 1924: 221) and the initiates were known under various names such as *poki manu*, “bird child”, *poki take* (the meaning of *take* is unclear) (Routledge 1914-1915: Reel 1: 0565), *vi'e huru*, “secluded girl”, (Reel 2: 0823), and *poki huru hare*, “child confined to the house” (Englert 1974: 163).

One particular group of initiates were called *neru*, which was translated by the natives as “virgins”. According to tradition, they were isolated in two remote coastal caves located in the north-eastern part of the island, Ana O Keke for girls and Ana More Mata Puku for boys

(Englert 1974: 182-184). Knoche who explored the island in 1911 was the first to record this practice: “This remote island also had some kind of Vestal virgins cult, whereby fathers secluded their daughters in caves, for the rest of their life or until they reached puberty” (1925: 191). He collected a chant in which these girls are called *neru* (1912: 70). This is an adapted transcription¹ and translation²:

<i>ate manava mate</i>	Song of longing
<i>ka huru koe neru e</i>	How secluded you were, o <i>neru</i> !
<i>ka huru kata</i>	How secluded (your) laughter was.
<i>ka rito-rito 'i te 'ana raro</i>	How white (you) became in that cave below,
<i>'i te 'ana tau-tau ipu ki'ea</i>	in that cave where the gourd with red ochre was hanging.
<i>o ŋā neru e tuai 'ā</i>	O <i>neru</i> of old!

The next researcher to gather information on the Easter Island initiation rites was Routledge who stayed on the island from March 1914 until August 1915. She was unable to obtain much information on a ritual that was called *take*, apart from the fact that it involved the seclusion of boys and girls in the caves of Motu Nui. This coastal islet was also connected to the famed birdman cult as the place where the annual search for the sacred bird egg took place. Apparently, this *take* rite had been abandoned thirty years before the arrival of the missionaries in the 1860s (Routledge 1919: 266).

More details were available on another ceremony called *te manu mo te poki*, “the bird for the child”. Under the supervision of certain experts, initiates called *poki manu*, “bird children”,

1 Reconstructed Rapanui texts follow the spelling of Kieviet (2017) as much as possible, i.e., the nasal velar is written as *ŋ*, long vowels are indicated by a macron.

2 All translations from non-English texts are by the author.

were shaved and decorated with stripes and figures of white paint and oval shaped wooden pendants called *tahoŋa*. They were brought in procession to Orongo, the ceremonial center of the birdman ritual, accompanied by song and dance (Routledge 1919: 267). Routledge makes no mention of the *neru* or a ritual fattening of children. She does, however, describe the custom of young people of both sexes to seclude themselves in *koro*-houses “to get their complexions good” in preparation for certain festivities (1919: 235).

Métraux, a member of the Franco-Belgian expedition of 1934-1935, first stated that the purpose of the seclusion was for the *neru* “to become white and stout” (1940: 104) but later changed his position: “... tradition does not refer to a fattening diet. There is nothing in the surviving recollection of the *neru* to suggest that it was a custom dictated by religion; on the contrary, a few allusions in a poem and a story stress the charms of these *neru* and imply that their confinement increased their beauty” (1957: 109-110).

Like Routledge, Métraux collected several chants about the initiates. However, the fact that his informants did not remember these texts as such lead him to misunderstand their meaning. An example of this is the following lament of a secluded girl, who is addressing her companions. Despite the fact that it contains very obvious references to an initiation ritual, Métraux published it as being about “a married girl who is shut in the house of her father-in-law” (1940: 357). This is an adapted transcription and a revised translation:

<i>e manu ē ka pari mai toto</i>	O “birds”, until (my) blood is spilled,
<i>hare kere ena ‘a ‘aku</i>	this gloomy house will be mine!
<i>‘i te po e manu ē</i>	In this darkness, o “birds”,
<i>e au ta‘e kai i te kumara</i>	I am not eating the sweet potatoes
<i>o tou korohua nei</i>	prepared by the old folk!
<i>ko mae ‘ā te reŋa</i>	This beautiful girl has grown pale!

Englert, the Roman Catholic priest on Easter Island from 1935 to 1969, was the last person who was able to gather new material on the initiation rites. His informant Tepano told him that the children who were secluded at home “only ate sugarcane, bananas, yams, and only in small amounts. Sweet potatoes are heavy, so they did not eat sweet potatoes³. Fish they ate too, but not much, only small quantities” (1939: 197). About the diet of the *neru* he said: “The only food was sugarcane” (1939: 209). According to another native: “They did not eat sweet potatoes, what they ate was sugarcane and shellfish” (1939: 208).

The informants of Englert and his predecessors seem to have been unaware of the purpose of the diet. Nevertheless, there can be little doubt that the high calorie food was used to fatten the secluded children in the same way as practiced by other Polynesian societies⁴. It was, for instance, remembered in an account of a much later date: “According to Emilia Kaituoe, her maternal grandmother was secluded inland from Hanga Ho‘onu bay and was so heavy when the day of celebration arrived that she was unable to walk. The girl’s father and uncle exhibited her by carrying her on their shoulders and she was considered the most beautiful girl present” (Edwards and Edwards 2013: 261).

Another indication that fattening was an essential part of the initiation is found in the term *neru* itself. It was translated by native informants as “virgin” but since it does not have cognates with this meaning in other Polynesian languages, it is more likely related to Hawaiian *nelu*, “fat”, “fleshy”, “plump”, and Māori *ngerungeru*, “to be obese”, “to be shaking with fat” (Tregear 1891: 283). The word appears for the first time – as *nire*, “virgin” – in the vocabulary collected by Thomson in 1886 (1891: 551). Its earliest spelling as *neru* occurs in the chant recorded by Knoche in 1911 that was cited above. Its presence, however, is obscured as it is printed as fused with vocative particle *e* as *nerue* and translated as a term of

3 As sweet potatoes are nourishing but low on calories, they would have counteracted the fattening.

4 The Tahitian custom of *ha‘apori*, “fattening”, for example, had a comparable diet of *popoi*, a fermented dish of “fruit, bananas, and mashed breadfruit mixed with water” (Moerenhout 1837: 286).

endearment, “Kleine” [little one]. The confusion about the term is best illustrated by Brown’s “The Riddle of the Pacific”, in which the term *neru* is compared with Māori *ngeru*, “smooth”, “soft”, “sleek” (1924: 286). The word – also spelled as *niru* (1924: 221) – is first explained as “virgin” (1924: 85) and later as “a man with long nails who does not work” (1924: 286). The latter description clearly refers to the forced idleness in which the secluded children had to spend their days. In the words of Tepano: “Their nails grew long, their hair grew long. It fell on their feet; the hair of the *neru* was like clothing covering their body” (Englert 1939: 209). The use of the ceremonial locations of Motu Nui and Orongo and the fact that the initiates were called “bird children” could point to some connection to the birdman ritual. In the same way as the birdman appears to have taken on the appearance of a bird by growing his hair and nails, the children’s fatness, white skin, and long hair and nails may have been intended to mimic the plumpness, white plumage, and claws of the young frigate bird.

It is more than likely that a prolonged stay in humid and cramped quarters such as Ana O Keke in combination with an unhealthy diet had severe repercussions on the children’s physical and mental condition. After the disappearance of the custom⁵, these aspects seem to have been largely forgotten. In the songs dedicated to the *neru*, the children are chiefly remembered for their “beauty”.

Englert was the first to investigate the two *neru* caves located on the steep cliffs of Poike peninsula⁶. In Ana O Keke, the “Cave of the Setting Sun”, which has also been called “Cave of the White Virgins”, he discovered a 4m long petroglyphic mural stretching over the right

5 According to Englert (1974:145), the *neru* cult had already been abandoned decennia before the coming of the missionaries in the 1860s. Métraux, on the other hand, was told that many secluded children starved after their parents had died in the smallpox epidemic of 1863 (1940:104).

6 This location had already been pointed out to Routledge and Métraux, but both neglected to examine it. Routledge writes in her field notes on Poike: “Mahunga Paréhé (...) below it cave TENIRO on waterline” (1914-1915: Reel 2: 0361). Métraux remarks that “two caves in Poike” were pointed out to him “which were said to have been inhabited by *neru*” (1940: 104).

wall of the first chamber (fig. 1). These engravings are extremely interesting as they contain a number of figures that stand in obvious relation to some of the glyphs inscribed on wood. The intricate designs not only suggest that the cave was an important cult site but also that *rongorongo* writing may have had some function in the *neru* rituals.

Fig. 1: The petroglyphs at Ana O Keke (adapted from Steiner 2008: 311, fig. 17)

Native attempts at decipherment linking *rongorongo* writing to initiation rites

The presence of petroglyphs at Ana O Keke is not the only instance where the *rongorongo* script makes its appearance in the context of coming of age rites. On three separate occasions, natives of Easter Island explicitly associated the writing with pre-missionary initiation practices. For the first time this occurred in 1886 when the American explorer Thomson and his Tahitian-born interpreter Salmon confronted an Easter Islander named Ure Vaeiko with photographs of inscribed tablets. Although the 83-year old produced five texts to these inscriptions, the researchers quickly learned that he was not reading the signs but reciting from memory.

As we only have Salmon's erratic transcriptions and jumbled attempts at translation, it is impossible to establish to what degree Ure Vaeiko himself understood the texts he was chanting⁷. This notwithstanding, reconstructed and retranslated selections of three of the recitations will show that the old man connected at least three tablet inscriptions to the ritual seclusion of children.

The chant that was supposedly recited to a reproduction of tablet C, was published under the headings "Ate-a-renga-hokan iti poheraa" and "Love song" (Thomson 1891: 526). Reconstructed to *ate o reŋa hōrau 'iti pohe ra 'ā*, this translates as "Song about a pretty girl, moving slowly and longing for the sun". Similar to the previous example, the chant uses bird imagery to refer to a secluded girl.

ka taŋi reŋa 'ā manu haka-opa How that pretty girl is crying, that "crippled bird"!

(...)

ka taŋi 'ā te uha 'iti-'iti How that "little hen" is crying!

he aha to 'ou teina e te hoa What is your little sister doing, o brother?

⁷ For a more detailed discussion, cf. De Laat 2014.

<i>taŋi teina 'i te hare huru 'ā</i>	(Your) little sister is crying in that house of seclusion,
<i>'i te hare huru 'ā mo nire⁸</i>	in that house of seclusion for virgins,
<i>haka-hiti 'i te ori miru</i>	(but) (she) will reappear at the festival of the Miru tribe,
<i>ana piri atu</i>	when (you) will be together again!

In the recitation to tablet D, an initiate is addressed by a parent or another relative (Thomson 1891: 525). The place of seclusion is clearly identified as a cave.

<i>'i ruŋa i te papare henua</i>	(Standing) above this entrance into the earth ⁹ ,
<i>veveri rahi inaŋa – o</i>	(my) heart is very moved, oh!
<i>hā'aki e ava henua</i>	But (I) promise: this hole in the earth
<i>ki taŋa atu – aue poki ē</i>	will have to let (you) go, poor child,
<i>ava rari – ava mata</i>	this damp hole, this dripping hole!
<i>'ina heva aue poki ē</i>	(You) will no longer have sorrow, poor child,
<i>'ite reŋa</i>	(you) will see (your) beauty!

The third and longest recitation by Ure Vaeiko that is related to the seclusion of children is called “Atua Matariri” and was “read” from tablet R (Thomson 1891: 520-522). Although scholars have generally regarded it as a rare example of traditional Rapanui literature, it was probably interpreted and styled as a procreation chant by Salmon after Tahitian examples. Some reconstructed fragments will demonstrate that the actual subject matter is not procreation but initiation as they mention the isolation in a dark and muddy cave, the fattening, the sugarcane, the bleaching by the avoidance of sunlight, and the health issues

8 Although the published text has *moni e*, it is proposed that the term *neru* is present here as *nire*, the term that appears translated as “virgin” in Thomson’s wordlist (1891: 551).

9 This fits Ana O Keke: on the edge of Poike’s cliffs one is standing some 20m above the cave’s entrance.

resulting from this. The purpose of the ritual is referred to as *rori*, which is best translated as “transformation”. The menarche appears to have signalled the end of the seclusion.

<i>ki ai ki roto ka tei</i>	(She) has to stay inside until (she) has grown.
(...)	
<i>ki ai ki roto</i>	(She) has to stay inside,
<i>‘āriŋa rehe huru a raro</i>	(with) a flabby face and hair to the ground.
(...)	
<i>ki ai ki roto hio-hio</i>	(She) has to stay inside (and) become fat.
(...)	
<i>ki ai ki roto ka tea</i>	(She) has to stay inside until (she) is white.
(...)	
<i>ka pu te toa ira pupuhi</i>	Bring on the sugarcane, look at (her) puffiness!
(...)	
<i>ki ai ki roto kai ruhi</i>	(She) has to stay inside, eating sweet foods,
<i>kai ruhi haka-maruhi</i>	sweet foods (that) make (her) paralytic.
(...)	
<i>ki ai ki roto maeha</i>	(She) has to stay inside (and) grow pale.
<i>ka pu te hera-hera tiko mea</i>	Bring forth the spread of the red menstrual flow!
(...)	
<i>e timo te ra ‘ā</i>	(She) deplores the sun,
<i>e mea a mu ‘a</i>	(she) was tanned before,
<i>i hii ki te aro</i>	because (it) shone on (her) body.
(...)	
<i>ki ai ki roto ka rori</i>	(She) has to stay inside, until (she) is transformed.
(...)	

<i>ki ai ki roto tau rare</i>	That soiled beauty has to stay inside.
(...)	
<i>ki ai ki roto ru pe rua</i>	(She) has to stay inside, shivering as if (she) was sick.
(...)	
<i>turu hero-hero te toto o te kovare</i>	The blood of the discharge will stream down red.
(...)	
<i>e‘a ‘ana ki hōrou</i>	(She) will leave that cave in a hurry.
<i>he aha e toe</i>	What will remain (with her)
<i>to tanu to ta‘ana moko</i>	of that interment, of her living underground?
<i>he aha hāηai</i>	What is going to nourish (her)?
<i>e toa e uhi e kumara</i>	Sugarcane? Or yams and sweet potatoes?

The second native attempt at decipherment was undertaken around 1915, probably by a man named Pua Ara Hoa ‘a Rapu, who was also one of the informants of Routledge. It has been preserved in the Esteban Atán manuscript published by Heyerdahl (1965: 413-415; fig. 111-121)¹⁰. In this case isolated signs were taken from a transcription of the Santiago Staff (text I) published by Philippi in 1875, arranged in a new order, and matched with texts describing an initiation ritual involving children called *poki manu* and *poki take*. Some reconstructed fragments:

<i>he poki motu ‘i te kohau</i>	The (names of the) children are inscribed on the tablets
<i>e ma‘ori o te kohau</i>	by the masters of the inscriptions.
(...)	
<i>ketu i te hahine kokoro</i>	Should a voluminous woman be praised?
<i>herere tau rā he taηata</i>	Should people confine a beautiful girl

¹⁰ Recently, an incomplete version of this text has surfaced (Horley and López Labbé 2014: 38-39).

ananake ko to 'ona mahiyo (or) should (she) be with her family?
 (...)

kua puru te ika The “sacrificial victims” are locked up
'i roto i te hare paeŋa e taŋata inside the boatshaped house by the people.
heŋu 'ā 'i te ao e taŋata The people resent (them) in the daylight
herere 'ā ki roto ki te pa he ika tao (so) those “cursed victims” are confined inside the
 walls.
 (...)

o roto i te koro Inside the *koro*-house,
haka-opo he toa (they) suck on the sugarcane
'o te ika poki vahine because the girls are “sacrificial victims”.
ka e 'a tau When those beautiful girls emerge,
pupuhi (they) will be bloated.
ka oho poki manu poki take e taŋata As long as those “bird children” and “*take* children” are
 abandoned by the people,
huru-huru (they) are secluded.
 (...)

haka-hetu 'u o roto i te koro taŋata (They) will be turned into “stars” in the *koro*-house
 by the people
ka maitaki te huru o te koro taŋata as long as the people approve of the seclusion
 of the *koro*-house.
puha (They) will grow fat
ka rava 'a-rava 'a te take tamahahine until the initiation of the girls is over,
'o tapu ara taha because that sloping path is forbidden (to them)¹¹.

¹¹ Possibly a reference to the narrow path leading from Ana O Keke to the top of the cliff.

Another chant which is part of the same manuscript was known as *He timo te akoako* after its beginning words (Heyerdahl 1965: fig. 127). This particular text has already been associated with the script since the 1860s, even to such an extent that for a while *timo* became synonymous with “inscribed tablet” (Fischer 1997: 272). Although the informants described it to Routledge as being “like the alphabet learned first”, they had no idea about the subject matter (1919: 248).

Fischer has identified *He timo te akoako* as a chant connected to the *neru*, characterizing it as “a vivid and ingenious jeering or taunting song whose purpose is to entertain and teach the young *rongorongo* males, through rhetorically making merry with the young *neru* females, their social counterpart” (1994: 437). Unfortunately, his forced attempt at reconstructing and translating it as such has resulted in a confused text that strays far from the original material (1994: 434). Instead, the chant can be interpreted as being of the same type as the other texts discussed here. The initial phrase probably refers to the “swallowing” (*aku-aku*) of food that is deplored (*timo*) by the initiates. They are described as *manu va’e eha*, “four-legged birds” – a reference to having to crawl on all fours in a narrow cave and/or the inability to walk upright resulting from fatness and inactivity – and as *kapa-kapa*, “flapping the wings”, *tetu*, “enormous”, *taha*, “bending over”, and *kui*, “staggering”. Some lines:

<i>he aha ana e noho ‘ana</i>	Why must (we) stay in this cave,
<i>‘i tu‘a te ‘ata-‘ata</i>	at the back, in the shadows,
<i>maru-maru kohu-kohu</i>	the darkness, and the gloom?
(...)	
<i>a tu‘a a ruŋa e</i>	Afterwards, above ground,
<i>para kava to uha</i>	these “hens” will be melancholic and embittered!
<i>aha ma‘a te riu hiki</i>	Why are (we) learning these <i>hiki</i> -dance songs
<i>mo noho ‘i roto i te pū</i>	if (we) have to sit in this hole?

(...)

he timo herere (We) deplore this confinement,
‘ana kē ahu ahe this special cave, this “swelling”, and these headaches!

The term *ahu* of the last line appears also in other *neru* chants but is usually misunderstood as referring to a stone platform. Another example of its use for the fattening of children can be found in a text recorded by Métraux in 1934/1935 and published by Barthel (1960: 850) which can be reconstructed as:

ka iri e mati ē ki te ahu Go up, o Mati, to the “swelling”!
titiro ko reŋa (You) will join the beautiful girls
‘i vaeŋa hue ‘i tu‘a te puakatiki in (their) gathering place behind Puakatiki¹².
ka amo ta‘au kai (You) must lap up your food,
e reŋa miti-miti ‘ā vai ē o juice sucking beauty!
mo te hare mo te ‘atua For the family, for the gods,
ma punua e tui ē (you) will be with the “hatchlings”, o exiled one!

The third occasion on which the *rongorongo* writing was connected to coming of age practices occurred when several of Routledge’s native informants claimed that the script played a part in the *manu* and *take* ceremonies. It was said that the *manu* children were given small tablets (1914-1915: Reel 2: 0726) and that the “*rongorongo* men” were involved in the *take* initiation: “The children wore birds, two back two front, and the birds were inscribed with *rongorongo*, made by *rongorongo* men. The *rongorongo* men looked after the children” (1914-1915: Reel 1: 0529)¹³.

12 The main peak of Poike pensinsula behind which the cliff with Ana O Keke is located.

13 Routledge’s field notes have been edited for abbreviations and spelling.

During several sessions, the informants supplied *manu* and *take* texts which they themselves poorly understood but which are clearly referring to the ritual seclusion of children. One such *take* chant was recited by an old man named Tomenika (1914-1915: Reel 2: 0814; Fischer 1997: 297) and can be interpreted as follows:

<i>ka tu'u mai e te take</i>	Come back to us, o <i>take</i> initiates,
<i>na 'a kahu para</i>	covered in (your) ragged clothes!
<i>rava 'a-rava 'a take</i>	The period of initiation is over!
<i>koai to tu'a</i>	Who is staying there in the back (of the cave),
<i>a ŋā kope ko mata mahore</i>	youngsters with (your) injured eyes?
<i>api rō tā 'ā me'e o kōrua</i>	Your circumstances give (you) a new color,
<i>e aka-aka nō ena</i>	(but) (you) can only move with great difficulty,
<i>e miti-miti ena</i>	and (you) have to lap up (your food)!

At some time before her arrival on the island, the old man had drawn four rows of imitation glyphs on a piece of paper¹⁴. He claimed that they represented the *He timo te akoako* chant (Routledge 1914-1915: Reel 2: 0815; 1919: 250) but another elder by the name of Kapiera provided a completely different interpretation (1914-1915: Reel 2: 0370-0379). Although difficult to understand, it is clear that the latter text was also connected to the initiation of young girls as it speaks of a “bird girl” (*manu tamahahine*), a “human sacrifice” (*ika tanata*) who is “secluded” (*huru*) in a “cave with beautiful girls” (*'ana ko reŋa*) to become “white” (*tea*) and who is “stuffed” (*komo*) with “sugarcane” (*toa*) and “banana flower juice” (*pi'o-pi'o*) to become “large” (*kotetu*) and “beautiful” (*reŋa*).

Texts such as these suggest that the *manu/take* rites were very similar to the *neru* cult as they too seem to have practiced seclusion, bleaching of the skin, and fattening of the body. In fact,

14 Reproduced in: Routledge (1919: fig. 99); Heyerdahl (1965: fig. 95).

there are so many overlaps in the scattered pieces of information on the Easter Island initiation practices collected by Routledge, Métraux, Englert, and others, that it is very well possible that they all describe different aspects of one and the same custom. This is not a new observation. Métraux, for example, considered *take* and *manu* as belonging to the same ritual, with the former referring to the period of seclusion and the latter to the concluding festivities (1940: 105-106). Similarly, Englert thought it possible that the *neru* ritual was simply another form of the *poki huru hare* custom (1974: 145).

Whether there was one initiation cult or several, fact is that certain groups of children were secluded in special houses or remote locations such as coastal and islet caves. The initiates were referred to as “birds”, “young birds”, “bird children”, *take* children, and as “fish”, i.e., “ritual sacrifices”. During their absence from society their skin was bleached and they were subjected to a special diet to fatten them in order to make them “beautiful”. Their return to society – likely as prospective marriage candidates – was accompanied by elaborate ceremonies in which they presented themselves with song and dance.

If it is assumed that the native informants were correct in their assertion that *rongorongo* texts and *rongorongo* men played an important role in these initiation rituals, a logical starting point for a decryption of the writing system would be to search the inscriptions for specific terms connected to these rites, such as “child” (*poki, tama*); “initiate” (*neru, poki manu/take*); “sacrificial victim” (*ika*); “menses” (*tehe, tiko, vari*); “seclusion”, “to seclude” (*hue, huru*); “cave”, “hole” (*'ana, ava, pū*); “beautiful (child)” (*tau, reŋa*); “white”, “pale” (*tea, rito-rito, mae, maeha*); “swollen”, “fat” (*ahu, puha, pupuhi*); “sugarcane” (*toa*).

As has already been mentioned in the introduction, given the number of basic glyphic elements in the inscriptions and the number of syllables in the language, the script is in all likelihood predominantly syllabic. At the same time, it can be hypothesized that – in accordance with other hieroglyphic scripts – the phonetic value of a number of signs has been derived from the name of the depicted objects. These two notions can serve as starting points

in the examination of the *rongorongo* inscriptions for terms related to the initiation of children. From these it will be possible to deduce some of the commonest glyphic elements. With these basic components other words can be traced, including some of the grammatical particles. This will in turn enable the translation of certain sequences of glyphs as short sentences. In this way, the construction of ligatures (fused signs) and the grammatical structure of the inscriptions will gradually become clear.

Petroglyphs and initiation terms as clues to phonetic values

Assuming that certain *rongorongo* inscriptions were indeed in some way connected to the initiation rituals, one of the

most obvious words to look for would be “child”, i.e., the glyph representing the word *poki* or *tama*¹⁵. Although the script has a number of anthropomorphic signs – such as the very common depictions of a standing and sitting man (fig. 2a-b) – none of these look particularly childlike. However, given the fact that in the traditions and chants connected to the rites the children are metaphorically referred to as “birds”, “bird children”, or “young birds”, it could be hypothesized that they were represented by an ornithomorphic glyph such as the one depicting a young bird of which fig. 2c-d are variants.

Given the fact that both the head and body of the bird glyph appear in combinations with other elements (e.g., fig. 2a-b;e), the figure is likely a ligature representing a disyllabic word. Similarly, the body of the upright standing man of fig. 2a is also used in other composites (fig. 2f), suggesting that this glyph too is a composite of two syllabic elements. Assuming that the sign was deliberately constructed to depict a human being, the only general term with two different syllables that seems to fit is *ta-ŋa-ta*, “man” or “person”. This would imply that a component can contribute its phonetic value more than once to the reading of a word, or, differently phrased, that an already present syllable needs not to be repeated¹⁶. (In the transliteration of such a sign in the illustrations, this “reduplicated” value will be added in parentheses.)

15 *Tama* has sometimes been taken for a Mangarevan or Tahitian loan. Against this can be argued that already in the 1860s Roussel collected the words *tamaahine*, “daughter”, and *tamaroa*, “boy” (1908: 203;241).

16 An additional advantage of this particular construction may have been that it could also represent the plural form *ŋāŋata*, “men”, “people”.

The idea that the “young bird” glyph also refers to a human being is supported by several parallel texts in which it is replaced by signs depicting people (fig. 3; see also fig. 31).

If it is assumed that the head of the human figure stands for the phonetic value *ta*, the glyph of the young bird can be speculated to read *ta-ma*, “child”. The petroglyph of a similar looking bird in a cave on the islet of Motu Nui (fig. 4) seems to corroborate this interpretation. As this was one of the places where initiates were isolated, it connects the symbol of the young bird to the ritual seclusion of children. If the reading *tama* is correct, “children” are clearly an important theme in the *rongorongo* texts as all the longer inscriptions have multiple occurrences of the glyph (in texts A, C, E, and I¹⁷, it even appears in the first line).

Fig. 4

The syllables *ta*, *ŋa*, and *ma* that have been assigned in this way, can serve as starting points in the search for

Fig. 5

other phonetic values. It can be deduced from parallel examples such as fig. 5a-b from texts H and P, respectively, that the human head and the head of the frigate bird are equivalents. From other parallel fragments in texts P (fig. 5c) and H (fig. 5d) follows that the phonetic value of the complete frigate bird is equivalent to that of the body minus the bird head. From this, in turn, can be hypothesized that both the full-body glyph and the body without the head represent the same value as the bird head and the human head, i.e., *ta*.

¹⁷ According to the numbering of Barthel which is followed in this paper, this is line 11 of the Santiago Staff.

However, Horley has convincingly argued that it is in fact the first line (2011: 35-41).

If the frigate bird sign reads *ta*, it would be interesting to interpret it in the context of initiation as “color”. In the vocabulary collected

by Roussel in the 1860s, the word *ta* has such meanings as “to color”, “to paint”, “to tattoo”, “to inscribe”, “to write” (1908). Recently, Albert Davletshin (2017: personal communication) has proposed the reading *mea*, “red”, for the “hatching” appearing in certain signs. There are a number of passages where the hatched “stick” appears in close proximity to the frigate bird (e.g., fig. 6a-b). In the present context, it could therefore be tentatively proposed that this sign, instead of *mea*, reads *tea*, “white”. This would result in *tā tea* (fig. 6a) and *tā tea-tea* (fig. 6b), “white color”, which could refer to the desired pale complexion of the secluded children. In addition, a phrase from text A could be read as *tea tama*, “The children are/become white” (fig. 6c).

With the notion that bird signs may refer to human beings and the identification of the *ma*- and *ta*-components, it is tempting to assign to

two other bird glyphs the respective readings of *mātou* and *tātou*, the exclusive and inclusive first person plural pronouns (fig. 7a-b). Occasionally, the long beak is replaced by a downward-facing head with an open mouth (fig. 7c). If it is assumed that *tou* was also used independently as *tohu*, “curse(d)”, a composite from text A could be read as *tama tohu*, “cursed children” (fig. 7d), which could be a reference to the fact that these children were declared taboo or to the miserable circumstances to which they were condemned.

With the identification of the syllable *ma*, it can furthermore be speculated that the sign which depicts the moon (*mahina*) in its crescent phase, was used to write the negator *ina* (fig. 8a)¹⁸. This is

18 Possibly, the sign is a depiction of a wooden breast ornament (*rei miro*), which may have been modelled after the crescent moon.

supported by the fact that the component is rare in fusions, with the exception of a ligature that can be read as *taina*, “sibling” (fig. 8b)¹⁹.

If the “open mouth head” of the human figure (fig. 2a) has the phonetic value *ta*, the rest of the figure must read *ηa*. This

“body” is part of a large group of composite glyphs of which the “big-eared man” (fig. 9a) stands out in terms of frequency. The only words with *ηa* that appear to match this are *anηa*, “to do”, “to make”, and *hanηa*, “to want”, “to accept”, “to like”, which would give the “head with ears” the value (*h*)*a*. The “stick” sign (fig. 9b) is likely an allograph of the “head” sign as can be deduced from fused signs in parallel passages from text A (fig. 9c-d) and from text P (fig. 9e) and H (fig. 9f)²⁰.

In some instances, the *tama* sign has an appendage resembling an outstretched leg as in fig. 10a. There is also an upright version of

this sign (fig. 10b). In the mural of Ana O Keke, the same element is found twice in the vaguely anthropomorphic figure that appears to be swimming or floating in the water (fig. 10c). Its conspicuously long nails identify it as a reference to the girls who inhabited the cave. As was mentioned before, according to tradition the *neru* had to let their hair and nails grow long. The fact that the “hands” are thumbless and the way the joints are bent – not as an elbow but as a knee – indicate that the sign is actually depicting a bent leg with toes. If the dot – a cupule that is part of the water line – is ignored, the central component can be recognized as a (*h*)*a* sign (fig. 10d). This means that the “swimmer” is a composite of two different

¹⁹ Its variant *teina* is used to refer to a secluded girl in one of the chants of Ure Vaeiko discussed above.

According to McCall (1980: 68), the term is also used for close friends of the same age group. As the inscriptions appear to be concerned with female initiates, it will be translated as “sister”.

²⁰ In text I, the “stick” is reduced to a single vertical line.

rongorongo signs representing a word with the structure ABA, AAB, or – with the middle element reduplicated – ABAB. Assuming that the term is somehow connected to the secluded children in the ritual context of Ana O Keke, a plausible value for the “leg turned arm” component would be *te*, giving *tetea* or *tea-tea*, meaning “white”, “pale”, “to shine”, etc. The phonetic value *te* may derive from *tehe*, “to come”, or *tere*, “to run”. With the possible exception of fig. 10e from text A, a *tea-tea* composite does not occur in the inscriptions on wood. An explanation for this is perhaps provided by the existence of the already discussed “hatched stick” as a more compact alternative.

Immediately below the “swimmer” petroglyph looms the large figure of what appears to be a whale (cf. fig. 1). A closer inspection, however, reveals that it is actually a depiction of a type of bottle gourd (fig. 11a), lying on its side. Apparently, the animal’s mouth and eyes have been left out to avoid compromising this identification. For the same reason, the two parallel

Fig. 11

lines that were added to the left side to give the impression of a bifurcated tail were kept separate from the main body. That the figure at Ana O Keke is not an accidental likeness is demonstrated by an engraving of a very similar gourd in one of the stone houses at Orongo (fig. 11b). The fact that this specimen encloses an unmistakable *rongorongo* glyph suggests that the gourd too should be interpreted as a sign.

This is also inferred by the appearance of its distinct figure in the inscriptions on wood – both with and without the rounded appendage on the narrow end (fig. 12a-c). One example from tablet C clearly shows that this attachment must be functioning as an independent component (fig. 12d).

Fig. 12

The same can be deduced from parallel text fragments where its usage is optional (fig. 13a-

b). As the appendage is usually attached to the right side of other signs, it could be representing one of the postverbal and/or postnominal particles of the language. It can be hypothesized that the structure of these phrases is either verb – x – subject – object (– x) or verb – x – object – subject (– x). In modern Rapanui, the candidates for “x” are the particles *ai*, *‘ā*, *‘ana*, *ena*, *era*, *nei*, *nō*, and *rō*, all of which may appear after the nucleus of both the verb and the noun phrase.

The most likely of these is *rō* as there also exists a stacked glyph consisting of two of these elements (fig. 14a-c). Rapanui *roro* means “head” or “skull” and in some composites it can be

found in the appropriate position (e.g., fig. 14d). The same figure appears to be part of the designs painted on the head of an Easter Island barkcloth figure in the collection of the Ulster Museum in Belfast (fig. 15a).

Possibly, the sign is related to the so-called “eye masks” which are a

prominent motif in the rock art of the island (fig. 15b). Tradition has associated these masks with the supreme god Makemake which is perhaps explained by a myth in which he is born from or incarnates in a skull (cf. Métraux 1940: 312-313).

The presence of the grammatical particle *rō* suggests that the “gourd” in Ana O Keke’s mural functions as a verb or a noun. The Rapanui terms for “gourd” are *kaha*, *ipu*, and *hue*. Of these, the latter is the most likely candidate as the words *kaha* and *ipu* do not have other meanings, whereas *hue* is also a verb meaning “to gather”, “to heap up”, “to hide”. More importantly, Englert (1974: 182) gives *Ana hue neru*, as the general name for the two caves in Poike where

children were secluded. He translates *hue neru* as “gathering or congregation of the *neru* girls”, but the name of the cave can also be interpreted as “cave where the *neru* are hidden”.

The shape of the “gourd” glyph and the way slightly different variants are assembled in the inscriptions (fig. 16a-b), indicate that it can be broken down into two basic *rongorongo* components

(fig. 16c-d). Assuming that these represent the syllables *(h)u* and *(h)e*, the phonetic value that applies to the “crescent” can be deduced from the sign’s double presence in a phrase from text A which can be read as *ta’e hue*, “not gather” or “not hide” (fig. 17a).

The value of the “crescent” is confirmed by the vocative construction *e ... ē* which appears in text E as *e tanjata ē*, “o man!” or “o people!” (fig.

17b). With the value *(h)u* assigned to the bulbous part of the gourd, a similar phrase in text C can be interpreted as *e tau ē*, “o beautiful girl(s)!” (fig. 17c).

The fact that the gourd in fig. 17a is turned to the left suggests that its purpose is to support the negation. Occasionally, *ta’e* itself is written in reverse (e.g., in fig. 9e-f). When signs or parts of signs are reversed without a negator present, it will be assumed that this was done to negate the phrase. These reversed signs will be marked by chevrons (angle brackets) in the transliteration of the illustrations and by *NEG* in the text. Excepted from this are signs that have been turned around for purely decorative purposes (as in fig. 17b-c).

Comparison of parallel texts indicates that the signs of the “crescent” and the “biconvex lens” are likely allographs. One compound glyph, for example, is

written both with a “crescent” (fig. 18a) and a “lens” (fig. 18b). The “hairs” of these composites are the abbreviated form of a sign that looks like a fern or feather and is one of the most common glyphs (fig. 18c).

Parallel fragments from texts A (fig. 19a) and Q (fig. 19b) with the sign taking the place

of the *rō*-particle suggest that it may have similar grammatical functions. If the value *ra* is assigned to it, its fusion with *e* (fig. 18a-b) could be read as the postnominal and postverbal demonstrative particle *era*.

Other fused signs could be transliterated as *ra'e*, “first” (fig. 20a), *raro*, “down”, “below” (fig. 20b), *harara*, “stiff”, “inflexible” (fig. 20c), and *ura-ura*, “red” (fig. 20d). On its

own, the “fern” sign could represent the demonstrative *rā* and the intensifying particle *rā*. Its phonetic value may have been derived from Rapanui *rau*, “leaf”, but it is also possible that it was originally imagined as a ray of the sun (*ra'ā*).

As a consequence of assigning the value *(h)e* to the crescent- and lens-shaped glyphs, it can be proposed that the sign depicting a “star” (*hetu'u*) has the phonetic value *tu*. Assuming that the word “star” was spelled as a combination

of these two components, the phrase in fig. 21 can be read as *hetu'u tau*, “beautiful star”. This is reminiscent of *ka tau koe e te hetu'u kē ē*, “How beautiful that extraordinary ‘star’ is!”²¹, a line that was recited to Routledge by Tomenika (1914-1915: Reel 2: 0744; 0815) and Kapiera (1914-1915: Reel 2: 0371; 0378)²². The comparison of the fairness of the initiates with that of stars also appears in the already cited text of Pua Ara Hoa ‘a Rapu: *haka-hetu'u o roto i te koro*, “(They) will be turned into ‘stars’ in the *koro*-house” (Heyerdahl 1965: 413; fig. 111).

The “star” glyph also functions independently as the verb *tu'u*, “to arrive” (fig. 22a). In combination

21 On the use of the expression *koe* + vocative phrase in third-person narratives, see: Kieviet (2017: 145).

22 It is the first line of Kapiera’s interpretation of Tomenika’s imitation glyphs.

with the *(h)a* “stick” it represents the directional particle *atu* (fig. 22a-b). Parallel texts of the latter phrase demonstrate that the marker can be attached to the nucleus in an abbreviated form. In the first example, the *a*-part is omitted (fig. 22c), in the second the *(h)a* “head” is also left out (fig. 22d).

The directional *atu* usually – but not exclusively – expresses movement (of a participant, object, or information) away from the speaker or towards the addressee. One exception to this is its “metaphorical” use to indicate the extent of a state or characteristic (Kieviet 2017: 356). This means that the phrase in fig. 23 can be read as *tau atu tanjata*, “The man is very handsome”.

The elements *ta* and *(h)u* are also fused with a third component (fig. 24a-b). By comparison with other ligatures such as fig. 24c-d, these “wings” can be identified as *ri*, giving reduplicated forms of *tahuri*,

“to return”, “to turn upside down”, “to transform”, and *hariu*, “to hold in esteem”, “to look kindly”, “to turn”.

A fragment from text B reads *tahuri-tahuri tā*, “(Their) color changes” (fig. 25a). Other combinations with *ri* are *tari*, “to carry”, “to lead away” (fig. 25b),

which also appears reduplicated as *tari-tari* (fig. 25c), and ‘*āriŋa*, “face” (fig. 25d).

As is shown by the short sentences in fig. 23 and 25a, preverbal tense marking by *e* or *he* is absent. Their interpretation is therefore very dependent on the context as they could also be understood as statements about the past or the future or as questions. The absence of certain markers, in particular the article *te*, the most common word in the language, has already been suggested by Butinov and Knorozov who thought it plausible “to assume that the written language of Easter Island is a primitive hieroglyphic in which the auxiliary parts of speech

and affixes may easily be omitted” (1957: 16). A similar position was taken by Fedorova whose frequency analysis showed her “that these morphemes (*he* and *te*) are either lacking in the *kohau rongorongo* texts, or are employed considerably less frequently” (1963: 45)²³.

The fact that the article *te* was omitted is consistent with the relatively low frequency and the uneven distribution pattern of the “leg” sign *te*. The independent sign could instead represent the verb *tehe*, “to flow”, “to spread”, “to dissolve”, a term that is also used for the menses: *tehe tama tau*, “The beautiful children (will) menstruate” (fig. 26). Possibly, the same verb appears reduplicated in the name of a cave which is given by Métraux as “Ana-tetehe-tama” (1940: 109).

When the “outstretched leg” is used in ligatures, the *te* sign is often found in combination with a “hand” or an appendage that is either forked or pointed. Some verbs and nouns have combinations with all three of these, for example, the verb *aha* or *hana* (fig. 27) and the noun *tama* (fig. 28).

This suggests that these components have a similar grammatical function, more specifically that they could be preverbal markers connecting the adverbial clause with *tehe* to the main clause.

To determine the phonetic value of the “arm with hand”, the analysis of another composite – which usually has the hand turned inward – can be used. Apparently, it has been constructed as a sitting man because it refers to a human being.

²³ Curiously, Fedorova then took this a step further by stating that the *rongorongo* inscriptions demonstrated that “the particle *he* and *te* did not exist in the ancient tongue” (1963: 46).

This is confirmed by the fact that it occurs as an equivalent of both *taŋata* (fig. 29a-b) and *tama* (fig. 30a-b). The

sign is composed of three elements, two of which have been identified thus far as *ta* and *te*. This means that the third element – the “arm with hand” – could stand for *(h)i*, giving *tētahi*, “other(s)”.

Occasionally, the sign appears in pairs which matches the expression *tētahi ... tētahi ...*,

“some ... others ...”. A fragment from text A shows this pair in an anadiplosic word order (fig. 31a). A very similar phrase from the same line provides further evidence of the relation between *tētahi* and *tama* (fig. 31b).

With the identification of the “arm with hand” as *(h)i*, other combinations can be read as *tahi*, “to erase” (fig. 32a), and *u'i*, “to look”, “to see” (fig. 32b). It can also be

proposed that the glyph representing a fish (*ika*) stands for *ka* (fig. 32c). This would mean that a combination of the two signs spells the word *ika*, “fish” or “victim” (fig. 32d).

The sign of the “fishing man” can be read accordingly as

taŋata ika, “human sacrifice” (fig. 33a). This *taŋata ika* appears in text A as an equivalent of *taina*, “sister” (fig. 33b) which suggests that both may be terms that refer to the secluded children.

The fish sign also occurs independently, which can be explained by the fact that *ka* is also a verb meaning “to ignite”, “to become furious”, and a grammatical particle which functions as an aspect and imperative marker.

The fact that in parallel texts the “hand” component often alternates with the “fork” has suggested to some scholars that they are allographs. However, judging from their behavior, it is more likely that they have comparable but not identical phonetic values and grammatical functions.

An element which meets both of these requirements is *ki*: phonetically, it could substitute for *i*, especially where this is glottalized, and, grammatically, *i* and *ki* have corresponding roles

in the nominal and verbal frames. Fig. 34a-b show examples taken from parallel lines, reading *taŋata ira*, “those people there”, and *taŋata kira*, “those people over there”, respectively.

Assigning *ki* to the “fork” makes it relatively easy to identify the very common word *hoki* which meanings include “also”, “back”, “again”, “to

return”, “to recover”, “to bring back”. The sentence in fig. 35a reads *tata tea hoki tā*, “The paleness (of the children) will be erased and (their) tan will return”.

Independently, the (*h*)*o* sign represents the preposition ‘*o*, expressing cause (“because of”), possessive preposition *o* (inalienable), and the marker of the negative optative ‘*o* (“lest”). An example of the first appears in the phrase *hariu-hariu ‘o aura’a tama*, “(We) hold (them) in esteem, because the children are precious” (fig. 35b).

Examples of the other two can be found in parallel texts P and Q,

respectively: *tata tā o tama*, “The color of the children is erased” (fig. 36a); *tata ‘o tā tama ‘ā*, “(It) is erased lest those children have color” (fig. 36b).

The identification of ‘o, “because of”, leaves *ana* and *mo* as possible values for the third element that occurs in the same position as markers *i* and *ki* to

Fig. 37

introduce the adverbial clauses in fig. 27-28. The correct reading of the “pointed arm without hand” can be indirectly established as it also appears as the continuous marker ‘*ana* (the equivalent of ‘*ā*) in the phrases of fig. 37a-b: *haŋa ‘ana tama i tehe*, “The children are accepted after (they) reach menses”; *tu’u rā tā ‘ana rā e ra’ā*, “(Their) complexion should be reached by the sun”²⁴. Since *mo* is not possible in these positions, the equivalent of *i* and *ki* in fig. 27-28 must therefore be the irrealis *ana*.

Contexts such as that of fig. 37a also show that the meaning of the “big-eared man” is *haŋa*, “to want”, “to like”, “to accept”, rather than *aŋa*, “to make”, “to do”. The term – which in general is best translated as “to accept” – appears, for

Fig. 38

example, in relation to the isolation of young girls from society in anticipation of the menarche: *ina haŋa rō atu taŋata ana tehe*, “The people do not accept (the children) if (they) menstruate” (fig. 38a).

In a number of cases, the sign for “menses”, *tehe*, is connected to the glyph for *to(h)u* (fig. 38b). In all likelihood, this should be interpreted as *tehe tohu*, “cursed flow”, which can be compared to the “cursed children” of fig. 7d. The fact that the menses is referred to in this way is indicative of the taboos surrounding the coming of age of young girls.

A term that therefore could also be expected is *tapu*, “taboo”. The texts discussed in the previous chapter include some words with which the syllable *pu* can be

Fig. 39

²⁴ The three “ferns” may be alluding to sunrays. Of interest is the presence of the normally omitted agentive *e* serving as support for the “sun” sign. The “crescent with bulge” is a variant of the “crescent” sign.

traced: *pū*, “hole”; *puha*, “to grow fat”; *pupuhi*, “puffed up”, “bloated”, “out of breath”, “to swell”. Phrases that incorporate the “walking cane” sign of fig. 39a provide the best matches for these terms. A sequence from text G, for example, can be interpreted as *‘ina haŋa pū u ‘i mātou*, “(We) do not like the hole that we saw!” (fig. 39b).

Another sentence juxtaposes the term for Fig. 40

“hole” with its homonym *pū*, “to meet”: *pū*

mātou / *pū NEG mātou ‘ā pū roa pū*, “Are we

in contact with (our) children? We do not meet (them) ourselves, (because) that hole is a remote hole” (fig. 40).

The segments of fig. 39-40 are Fig. 41

interesting as they both suggest that there

is a group of people that is critical of the

practice of seclusion. Their rejection appears to be directed mainly at the fattening of children.

A fragment from text H, for example, states: *puha ‘ina tama ‘ā / ‘ina taina heka*, “Those children should not grow fat. (Their) sisters are not flabby” (fig. 41).

The same sentiment is expressed in text E: ‘o

Fig. 42

tama e NEG ta ‘e haŋa i puhi-puhi, “Because

(they) are children, (we) should not accept that

(they) are bloated” (fig. 42). In this example, the negator *ta ‘e* – written in reverse – appears to be mimicking the *tama* sign.

With the identification of the glyph for *pu*, the

Fig. 43

phrase in fig. 43 which has the reduplicated form

of the verb *tapu* can be read as *tatapu era taŋata*

i tehe taina, “The people declare (them) taboo because (our) sisters menstruate”, but given the context it is more likely a question: “Should the people declare (them) taboo because (our) sisters menstruate?”

As already noted, the traditions have two terms for the seclusion resulting from this taboo: *hue* and *huru*. The first is written with the gourd composite, the second, for which the syllabic sign for *ru* is needed, can be traced by taking another look at the petroglyphs of Ana O Keke. Panel B has two figures that look like *rongorongo* glyphs: the “headless body” –

Fig. 44

resembling the *ηa* sign – and the cruciform (fig. 44). They are engraved near the upside-down figure of a dance paddle²⁵. From top to bottom they could therefore read *ηa-ro*, “to go down”, “to sink”. However, since the value *ro* has already been assigned to another glyph, it is possible that the spelling was *ηa-ru* instead, resulting from the language’s “unconditioned allophonic alternation of the unstressed vowels *o* and *u*” (Fischer 1997: 583).

If this assumption is correct this would give *huru*, “to seclude”, as a possible reading for the first sign in fig. 45a-b. As this ligature has been thought to be

Fig. 45

the image of the extinct Easter Island palm tree, its construction could perhaps be explained by the word *uru* meaning “grove” in some closely related languages. The “palm tree” sign appears in several combinations which confirm that the girls’ menses was the primary reason for their seclusion, e.g., *huru tama ana tehe*, “(We) seclude the children if (they) menstruate” (fig. 45a), and *huru 'ana tohu 'ā mā-tou*, “We seclude that ‘curse’ ” (fig. 45b). Again, it is important to note that statements of this type could easily have been questions in this context. The last two sentences, for example, could also be interpreted as expressing doubts regarding the initiation customs: “Should (we) seclude the children if (they) menstruate?” and “Should we seclude the ‘curse’?”

25 Possibly, this paddle (*rapa*) symbolizes Venus descending after sunset as the “Evening Star” while its upright counterpart in panel C refers to the planet rising before sunrise as the “Morning Star” (cf. fig. 1). Rapanui *rapa* also means “brilliant” which befits Venus as the brightest object in the sky after the sun and the moon. The fact that the fair *neru* were referred to as “stars” could point to a special relationship with the planet that was sometimes called *hetu 'u tea*, “white star” (cf. De Laat *in press*).

The terms *puha*, “to grow fat”, and *heka*, “flabby”, referring to the excessive overweight of the initiates in fig. 41 are

very rare. This suggests that there have been other terms for fatness and the process of fattening. A ready candidate is the ubiquitous “turtle” sign as it appears in two similar settings as *heka* (fig. 46; 49). The sign is constructed from a *(h)a* and a *(h)u* component and can therefore be read as *ahu*, “swollen”, “plump”, “to swell”. In this way, the sentences in fig. 46 can be interpreted as *ina huru era heka*, “Does the seclusion not make (them) flabby?” and *ina huru era ahu*, “Does the seclusion not swell (them)?”, respectively.

The meanings of “swollen” and “to swell” – which can be taken as synonyms of “fat” and “to

grow fat” – fit well in a number of contexts referring to the secluded children, e.g., *tama ahu*, “swollen children” (fig. 47a); *ahu tama ana*, “The children swell” (fig. 47b); *ahu tētahi tama puru*, “Other closed up children will grow fat” (fig. 47c).

The term also appears in combination with other references to the children:

ahu rō ika, “The sacrifices are growing fat” or “Should the sacrifices be swollen?” (fig. 48a); *taŋata ika ahu*, “swollen sacrifice(s)” (fig. 48b); *taina ahu*, “swollen sister(s)” (fig. 48c); *roro ahu*, “swollen head(s)” (fig. 48d).

In addition to their very similar configurations with *huru* (fig. 46), synonyms *heka* and *ahu* also appear preceded by an intricate composite sign constructed

of a *(h)a* head and a torso which has on one or on each side a *ki* and a *te* sign (fig. 49). As the “sitting figure” occurs in several other combinations, it is relatively easy to identify as the

causative prefix *haka*. Read as *haka-teki(-teki)*, “to make lame”, this would produce *haka-teki-teki heka*, “The flabbiness makes (the children) lame” (fig. 49a), and *haka-teki ahu*, “The fatness makes (them) lame” (fig. 49b).

In fig. 50 the

causative is linked to

tuu: ka haka-teki

haka-tuu haka-tuu e 'ina taina 'ana, “When (they) are made lame, (they) will be immobilized, but (our) sisters should not be immobilized”.

The inscriptions have another glyph

that is made up of the same

elements as the “turtle” sign, but in

reverse order. It can be read as *uha*, which literally means “hen”, but was also a very common reference to women. It appears as such in the phrase *haka-teki-teki ana NEG tama / haka-teki-teki uha 'ā tētahi 'ā*, “Would (they) be made lame if (they) were not children? Would women be lamed by other people?” (fig. 51).

The sign for *haka-teki(-teki)* appears to be

interchangeable with a very similar composite that

has “hands” instead of “forks”. This can be

explained by the fact that the term *haka-tei(-tei)*, “to grow”, “to cause to grow”, is also connected to the concept of fattening. The traditions relate how the children were mainly fattened on sweet foods such as sugarcane. As both causative forms appear in parallel texts H (fig. 52a) and P (fig. 52b) connected to the same word ending in *(h)a*, the “three circles” sign can be tentatively identified as *to*, giving *toa*, “sugarcane”.

The latter combination also appears

in a segment of text A which

sarcastically contests the

association of beauty with fattening: *ka tau / haka-tei toa taina ahu rō era*, “How ‘beautiful’ (they are)! The sugarcane makes (them) grow (and so) (our) sisters are swollen” (fig. 53). Possibly, the “three circles” sign derives from *toru*, “three”.

The inscriptions mention not only sugarcane, fatness, and sitting in a cave as causes of the children’s

Fig. 54

lameness, but also the physical pain resulting from this: *e haka-teki-teki tata 'ana*, “That agony makes (them) lame” (fig. 54a). Another term for “pain” and “suffering” can be found in a fish-like figure by interpreting its wide open beak as a special form of reduplication (fig. 54b). If the facts that *mama* means “to gape”, “to open the mouth”, that the tail resembles a (*h*)e glyph, and that *mamae* means “pain”, “illness”, are combined, the sentence can be read as *haka-teki-teki mamae rā*, “Those pains make (them) lame”.

The “wide open beak” is also part of another composite which reads *māmate*, the

Fig. 55

reduplicated form of *mate*, “death”, “to die”, “to be very sick”. Two segments in text A have the terms *mamae* and *māmate* in identical positions. They appear in combination with a third composite which possibly reads *haoa*, “wounded”²⁶: *mamae tētahi tētahi haoa*, “Some are in pain, others are wounded” (fig. 55a), and *māmate tētahi tētahi haoa*, “Some are dying, others are wounded” (fig. 55b).

Another fish sign which has fins and a smaller mouth (fig. 56a) also appears in combination with

Fig. 56

the *e* sign (fig. 56b). Fig. 56c-d from parallel texts P and H indicate that this composite is in some way equivalent to *ahu*. As the seclusion was focussed on fattening and bleaching, the

²⁶ It has been assumed that the middle element is (*h*)u, i.e., the word is spelled as *haoa*.

composite could possibly read *mae*, “pale”, “to fade”. In this way, three similarly structured phrases can be interpreted as *mae ki NEG hue*, “Will (the children) be pale when (they) are no longer secluded?” (fig. 56c), *ahu ki NEG hue*, “Will (they) be fat when (they) are no longer secluded?” (fig. 56d), and *tata ana NEG hue*, “Will (they) be in agony if (they) are no longer secluded?” (fig. 56e).

Two other examples with *mae* read *mae ki huru 'ana*, “(The children) will become pale when (they) are secluded” (fig. 57a), and *mae 'ana tama*: “The children will become pale” (fig. 57b).

The phonetic value *ma* for the shark with the smaller beak may derive from *maŋo*, the name of a shark species. Possibly, the “bird body” element *ma* that was discussed before originated from the “open mouth” part. The independent shark sign of fig. 56a appears to represent the verb *ma'a*, “to know”, “to experience”, “to remember”, “to recognize”.

The phrase in fig. 58a contains the last of the series of particles that introduce the adverbial clause, *mo: hue mo tea*, “(The children) are secluded to become

white”. Two parallel segments from texts H and G, respectively, show how the object of *haŋa rō ahu*, “Should (the children) accept the fatness?” (fig. 58b), is turned into an adverbial clause by preverbal marker *mo: haŋa rō mo ahu*, “Should (they) accept (it) if (they) grow fat?” (fig. 58c).

This *mo* glyph is the simplified form of another shark sign (fig. 59)²⁷. In particular, fig. 59d-e from texts T and I, respectively,

²⁷ Curiously, some researchers have taken the stylized variants of this sign for a depiction of a phallus (e.g., Barthel 1958: 280; Fischer 1997: 259).

are crucial phases in this series as they illustrate the transition from two fins to a single protuberance. Possibly, the sign’s phonetic value was derived from *moŋo*, another term for “shark” (Roussel 1908: 237)²⁸.

The *mo* appendage gives text I its unique structure as it is fused with nearly every third or fourth sign. This

Fig. 60

omnipresence is facilitated by the multiple functions of *mo* as benefactive preposition (“for”) and preverbal marker (“if”, “because”, “to”). Some examples of these from this text are: *mo hue rō ahu rō 'ā*, “If (they) are secluded, (they) will grow fat” (fig. 60a); *ahu mo tau toa*, “The sugarcane fattens (them) to be beautiful” (fig. 60b); *ahu mo mamae*, “Should (they) grow fat if (they) suffer?” (fig. 60c).

The bleaching of the skin is also present as a topic in this inscription: *huru mo ura*

Fig. 61

mātou, “We seclude (them) because (their complexion) is red-brown” (fig. 61a).

The oval sign with the four pointed extensions that encapsulates *ura* in fig. 61b is a candidate for the syllable *po* and the word *pō*, “darkness”, “to darken”, as it appears to visually underline the meaning of the phrase: *huru mo pō ura*, “(They) are secluded to obscure (their red-brown (complexion))”. Fig. 61c gives an example of its use as a noun: *haŋa mo tea nō pō*, “(We) accept (it) if the darkness whitens (them) completely”.

Sentences from other texts support this interpretation. In text E, for example, it says: *haŋa pū pō*, “Should (the children) accept that

Fig. 62

²⁸ At one time, Easter Island may have possessed both *maŋo* and *moŋo* as names for two different species of shark. On the Marquesas, for example, large sharks are called *mako* and small ones *moko* (Lee 2004: 33).

dark hole?” (fig. 62a), while text C states: *tahuri-tahuri tama tehe pō / tahuri-tahuri u'i*, “The menstruating children are completely changed by the darkness, (their) eyesight is completely changed” (fig. 62b).

The Rapanui term for “blind”, *matapō* (“dark eyes”), can be compared to the expression *u'i pō*, “dark sight”, in text R: *haya 'ana hoki ki*

haka-hoki mai u'i pō, “Will (the children) also like (their bodies) when (their) blinded eyesight recovers?” (fig. 63).

The sentence in fig. 64a gives another example of the sign that is a likely candidate for the directional particle *mai*:

mamae mai roro u'i, “(The children’s) head and eyesight are in pain”. Fig. 64b also contains an example of *mai* as preposition “from”, “since”: *mamae mai mai ahu*, “(The children) suffer from (their) fatness”.

The limitative marker *nō* that is fused with the verb *tea* in fig. 61c appears in both the verbal and the nominal frame. The marker takes on different shapes

as is shown by other combinations with the verb *tea* (fig. 65). Its one to five elements are shaped as “lumps”, “thorns”, or “rectangles”, and may be attached to each side of the main glyph.

The sign can be identified as a grammatical marker by comparing related verbal phrases such as *aha era tuhi nō 'ā*, “Why are (the children) still blamed?” (fig. 66a), *aha era ta'e tuhi nō 'ā*, “Why is (their seclusion) not

criticized at all?” (fig. 66b)²⁹, *ta'e tuhi nō era*, “(They) should not be blamed anymore” (fig. 66c), *ta'e tuhi rā tā ira NEG tētahi*, “(Their) color should not be criticized by other people” (fig. 66d).

Similar to the *ra* glyph, the sign can also be written with a “stem” of its own. In fig. 67, the two variants are forming the verb *nono'i*: “to bend”, “to worship”: *nono'i tanata i ahu*, “People are worshipping (the children) because (they) are fat”.

The marker *nō* is frequently found fused with *tētahi*, “others”, giving *tētahi nō*, “some” (fig.

68). The reason for these many guises is not clear.

A variant of the sign represents the verb *noho*, “to sit”, “to occupy”, “to stay” (fig. 69a). This term is also used to refer to the

seclusion: *ma'a noho uha 'ā*, “The women should experience staying (in the cave) themselves” (fig. 69b). In text I, the expression *noho 'ana*, “to occupy a cave”, occurs frequently, e.g., *pō mo noho 'ana u'i*, “(The children’s) eyesight grows dark because (they) live in a cave” (fig. 69c).

From the text fragments that have been used thus far to identify some of the most common glyphs, a coherent picture emerges which ties in with the views formulated in the chants that were discussed previously. The themes of these fragments can be arranged into four groups, each of which can be illustrated by further examples:

1. The first group which describes the cult and its

²⁹ He was omitted from *he aha*, “why?”

consequences is best represented by a segment from the verso side of tablet G (fig. 70). This series which resembles the structure of the text I has been identified as a genealogy by Butinov and Knorozov (1957: 15). However, with the interpretation of the appendage as *mo*, the sequence can be read as *ahu mo haŋa ahu / mae mo haŋa mae / mara roro mo haŋa roro mara*, “(The children) grow fat because (we) accept fatness. (They) grow pale because (we) accept paleness. (Their) minds deteriorate³⁰, because (we) accept deteriorated minds”³¹.

Another sentence of the same text contains a rare fusion of the *mo* syllable with *e*, giving *moe*, “to

sleep”, “to lie down”. As it appears, the children were unable to stand on their own feet due to their excessive weight: *ta’e u’i ka moe tētahi nō*, “Don’t (you) see that some (of them) have to lie down?” (fig. 71a). Another negative aspect of the seclusion that is mentioned in this text is the vulnerability of their skin to the sun: *haoa tama mo tutu tā*, “The children will be harmed if (their) complexion is scorched” (fig. 71b).

Examples such as these amply demonstrate that the prolonged stay in the caves of Poike and Motu Nui in combination with an unhealthy diet and a lack of sunlight

and exercise had severe repercussions on the physical and mental condition of the initiates. A century after the disappearance of the practice this was still remembered. In the 1930s, Teao told Englert: *Ana ea-mai te neru kiruŋa kiroto ki te taŋata, he-mamate; ké mo mate, ké mo ora*, “When the *neru* reappeared among the people, they tended to become ill; some died, others recovered” (Englert 1939: 208). The very same notion can be found in text B: *māmate tētahi hoki tētahi*, “Some die, others recover” (fig. 72).

30 As *mara* means “to rot”, the expression can be compared to *taŋata roro piro*, “man with a rotten brain”, i.e., “fool” (Englert 1974: 352).

31 These could also be interpreted as a series of questions starting with “Should they ...”.

2. The negative aspects of the practice of seclusion have lead certain people to question the validity of the customs. The expression of their doubt is a second important topic in the inscriptions. The notion of beauty associated with the children’s physical transformation, for example, seems to have become controversial.

On tablet E, this is expressed as *haŋa* ‘ā *hāŋai* / ‘o *tama* e *NEG ta’e haŋa*

tau / ahu tau tahuri-tahuri tau, “Should (it) be accepted that (they) are fed (that way)? Because (they) are children, that ‘beauty’ should not be accepted. That ‘beauty’ swells (them) up, that ‘beauty’ changes (them) completely” (fig. 73).

In text A, this “beauty” elicits similar skepticism: *haŋa tau i tu’u atu tama* /

ma’a taŋata NEG tama ‘ana, “Are (the people) going to like (their) ‘beauty’ when the children arrive? The people will not recognize the children!” (fig. 74)³².

The sign for *to* is used in similar contexts as *haŋa*. This can be explained by assuming that it can also represent the verb *to’o*, “to take”,

“to accept”, “to tolerate”, which would make it to some extent synonymous with *haŋa*.

The examples taken from texts A (fig. 75a), S (fig. 75b; 76a), and I (fig. 76b) express doubt regarding the various aspects of seclusion:

oho ‘o ‘ina to’o tehe, “Should (the children) be abandoned because (we) do not accept the

32 If *ma’a* can be understood as a sense verb, the word order would be V(e)SO, i.e., with zero marking of the object. Alternatively, the sentence could be interpreted as “The children will not remember the people”.

menses?"; to 'o pū roa-roa, "Should (they) accept (occupying) that remote hole?"; to 'o ahu harara, "Should (they) accept the fatness and the stiffness?"; to 'o mo haka-teki ahu: "Should (they) accept (it) if the fatness makes (them) lame?"

To this text P adds: *huru rō tohu 'ā i haka-teki*, "Should the 'curse' be locked away when (this) has lamed

Fig. 77

(them)?" (fig. 77a). In text S, the unwillingness on the part of initiates themselves is also a cause for doubt: *huru ana rotu tama 'ana*, "Should the children be secluded if (they) protest?" (fig. 77b).

A term that is frequently encountered in text I in this regard is *tano*, "(to be)

Fig. 78

right, correct" (fig. 78a). Usually it appears as negated form which somewhat resembles the negator *ta'e*. Some examples of its use are: *NEG tano mo tea*, "(It) is not right to be white" (fig. 78b); *ahu mo NEG tano*, "Should (the children) grow fat if (it) is not right?" (fig. 78c); *ahu mo mātou ka NEG tano 'ā*, "Should (they) grow fat for us when (it) is not right?" (fig. 78d).

3. A third important theme is the dilemma confronting those that are skeptical of the seclusion. In text I, the alternatives are

Fig. 79

formulated as *tari haŋa rō rō tohu nei / ahu taŋata 'ana mo NEG tano*, "Should (we) lead (the children) away (or) really accept this 'curse'? Should people fatten (them) if (it) is not right?" (fig. 79). The first sentence contains a candidate for the demonstrative *nei*, here indicating that the 'curse' has been mentioned before.

The same choice between Fig. 80

isolation or acceptance of
the menses is presented in

text H as *tari-tari tama e haŋa tehe*, “Should (we) lead the children away (or) should (we) accept the menses?” (fig. 80a) and, again, in text I as *haŋa ki tehe ‘ā tari mo tā*, “Should we accept (them) when (they) reach menses (or) should (we) lead them away because (they) are tanned?” (fig. 80b).

4. The fourth theme is the answer that is given to the dilemma in all the major inscriptions: an unequivocal rejection of the taboos surrounding menses and a call for the termination of the practices of isolation, fattening, and bleaching.

Text H, for example, clearly states: ‘*ina* Fig. 81

huru era ana haka-teki nō, “(We) should
not seclude (the children) if (they)

become completely lame” (fig. 81a). On the subject of bleaching, it says in text I: *haŋa rō mo ura*, “(We) should accept (them) if (they) are red-brown” (fig. 81b).

A similar notion is found in text R: *NEG* Fig. 82

tahi-tahi ‘ā ‘ina tā taŋata ‘ā / ‘ina huru
era: “(We) should not erase (their) human

color. (We) should not seclude (them)” (fig. 82).

To determine who the “we” are that are repeatedly encountered voicing their dissension, it is necessary to first identify the people they are holding responsible for the cult practices.

This group is mostly referred Fig. 83

to as *tētahi*, “other people”,
but this can be narrowed
down by comparing two

fragments from text H (fig. 83). The first reads *ta'e tuhi rā tā rā tētahi 'ana rā*, “The

Conclusions

Using as starting point the assumptions that the *rongorongo* script is syllabic and that some phonetic values of glyphs derive from the represented objects, this paper has explored the notion of Easter Islanders like Pua Ara Hoa ‘a Rapu, Tomenika, and Kapiera that certain inscriptions played a role in pre-missionary coming of age rites. The traditions and chants about the initiates and their seclusion have provided the input for calculated guesses at the phonetic value of some of the most frequently occurring glyphs. As it appears, the basic elements of the script are mostly (C)V syllables, complemented by a limited group of disyllables. Both types can function independently as word-sign and as part of compound glyphs. The preferred reading order of the latter is from left to right and/or from top to bottom. The script lacks separate marking of consonants *h* and glottal stop and of vowel length. Allographs appear to have been designed to facilitate the construction of anthropo- and zoomorphic figures and to distinguish between homonyms.

From the rudimentary phrases that have been pieced together, some further principles of *rongorongo* can be deduced. The pre- and post-positional markers of the nominal and verbal frame are generally affixed to the nucleus which explains why the average composite sign has more elements than the average word has syllables. As already observed by Russian researchers, the writing system is to a certain extent defective. Most notable is the omission of some of the commonest words of the language: verbal markers *e* and *he* and article *te*. The reason for this may have been the saving of precious writing space as other strategies such as stacking, miniaturization, and reduplication of phonetic values seem to have served the same purpose. The transitive sentences in the examples suggest that the syntax of the inscriptions is predominantly VOS despite the fact that the neutral word order of the language is VSO. One explanation for this could be that in this way the object marker *i* was avoided while the agentive marker *e* could be omitted in accordance with the preverbal markers *e* and *he*. In

addition to negators *ta'e* and *'ina*, negation is indicated by reversing (part of) a sign or by turning it upside down. Both the preferred word order and the alternatives for negation may have originated as supplementary strategies for saving space.

The interpretations presented in this paper support native claims of a connection between script and initiation rites. However, this relation appears to have been a different one than was imagined as the *rongorongo* texts show a thematic correspondence with a specific group of chants that make mention of the negative aspects of the initiation rites. While the latter are not overtly critical, the inscriptions on wood give voice to a particular segment of society that unequivocally condemns the practices of seclusion, bleaching, and fattening.

Although the preliminary results presented here solve a number of problems regarding the Easter Island script, they also raise a very puzzling new one: how can it be explained that the majority of the longer inscriptions focus on a seemingly minor part of the cultural belief system? For the present moment, it is not possible to offer more than a general direction in which a solution may be sought. From the existence of the large corpus of orally transmitted texts it can be deduced that the initiation cults played a far more important role in pre-missionary society than can be learned from the ethnological publications. An often overlooked aspect of these texts is that they show glimpses of the complex mythological framework in which the initiation rites were embedded. Some versions of the *He timo te akoako* chant, for example, mention Tangaroa, the great Polynesian god of the ocean who was also associated with darkness, death, and afterlife, suggesting that he and the secluded “fish” were in some way connected. A “prelude” to this chant that was collected by Routledge (1914-1915: Reel 1: 0526) can be tentatively reconstructed as: *te 'atua nui te 'atua matu'a / he noho 'ana 'i tu'a te maru-maru 'i tu'a te 'ata-'ata o te raro te 'atua matu'a / ko te toto pari-pari o te raro na'a 'ana Tanjaroa te royo-royo 'a te 'atua matu'a*, “The parental god is the supreme god. The parental god resides in the darkness, in the shadows below. The blood flows below (where) Tangaroa and the disciples of the supreme god are hiding”. This concept

of the primeval god's presence among the secluded children can also be suspected in the petroglyph of the whale at Ana O Keke as the animal was regarded as one of Tangaroa's incarnations.

If the initiation rites played a key role in the traditional belief system, a discussion about their reformation or abolishment could have been regarded important enough to record and preserve. This, however, would only explain the presence of this particular subject matter in the inscriptions, but not why such a large part of the scarce wood resources was reserved for it. Even if the *rongorongo* script was used exclusively in a ritual context, one would expect a much wider range of topics than those emerging from the inscriptions. Unfortunately, the lacunae in our present knowledge of pre-missionary Easter Island society prevent a satisfactory answer to this problem. Hopefully, a more thorough understanding of the script and the inscriptions will open up new insights regarding this matter.

My sincere thanks go to Angeli Broekhuijsen and Berthold van Maris for reviewing the manuscript and to Hartwig-E. Steiner of the Institutum Canarium for his kind permission to reproduce his drawing of the petroglyphs at Ana O Keke and photograph of the petroglyph at Motu Nui.

References Cited

Barthel, Thomas S.

- 1958 Grundlagen zur Entzifferung der Osterinselschrift. Hamburg: Cram, de Gruyter & Co. (Abhandlungen aus dem Gebiet der Auslandskunde 64, Reihe B, vol. 36)
- 1960 Rezitationen von der Osterinsel. *Anthropos* 55: 841-859.

Brown, John MacMillan

- 1924 The Riddle of the Pacific. London: T. Fisher Unwin Ltd.

Butinov, N. A., and Knorozov, Y. V.

- 1957 Preliminary Report on the Study of the Written Language of Easter Island. *Journal of the Polynesian Society* 66(1): 5-17.

Edwards, Edmundo, and Alexandra Edwards

- 2013 When the Universe was an Island. Hanga Roa: Hangaroa Press.

Englert, Sebastian

- 1939 He Huru o Rapanui, Costumbres de la Isla de Pascua. *Revista Chilena de Historia y Geografía* 86: 184-215.
- 1974 [1948] La Tierra de Hotu Matu'a. Historia, Etnología y Lengua de la Isla de Pascua. Santiago: Editorial Universitaria.

Fedorova, I. K.

- 1963 On the problem of the nature of the language of the Easter Island texts. *Soviet anthropology and archeology* 2: 41-47.

Fischer, Steven Roger

- 1994 Rapanui's 'Great Old Words': E Timo te Akoako. *Journal of the Polynesian Society* 103(4): 413-443.
- 1997 Rongorongo. The Easter Island Script. History, Traditions, Texts. Oxford: Clarendon Press. (Oxford Studies in Anthropological Linguistics 14)

Frazer, J. G.

- 1913 The Golden Bough. A Study in Magic and Religion (Third Edition) Part VII: Balder the Beautiful Vol. 1. London: MacMillan and Co.

Heyerdahl, Thor

- 1965 The Concept of RONGO-RONGO among the Historic Population of Easter Island. In: Thor Heyerdahl and Edwin N. Ferdon (eds.), Reports of the Norwegian Archaeological Expedition to Easter Island and the East Pacific. Vol. 2: Miscellaneous Papers; pp. 345-459. Stockholm: Forum Publishing House.

Horley, Paul

- 2005 Allographic Variations and Statistical Analysis of the Rongorongo Script. *Rapa Nui Journal* 19 (2): 107-116.
- 2011 Palaeographic analysis of the Santiago Staff. *Rapa Nui Journal* 25(1): 31-43.

Horley, Paul, and Lilian López Labbé

- 2014 A new manuscript of Pua Ara Hoa 'a Rapu from the archives of William Mulloy, Part 1: Description of the manuscript. *Rapa Nui Journal* 28(2): 35-48.

Kieviet, Paulus

- 2017 A grammar of Rapa Nui. Berlin: Language Science Press. (Studies in Diversity Linguistics 12)

Knoche, Walter

- 1912 Ein Märchen und zwei kleine Gesänge von der Osterinsel. *Zeitschrift für Ethnologie* 44(1): 64-72.
- 1925 Die Osterinsel. Eine Zusammenfassung der chilenischen Osterinselexpedition des Jahres 1911. Concepción: Verlag des Wissenschaftlichen Archivs von Chile.

Laat, M. de

- 2014 Ascension: proposal for a reconstruction of Ure Vaeiko's *Apai* recitation. *Rapa Nui Journal* 28(1): 23-37.
- in press* Phonetic values in the petroglyphs at Ana O Keke, Easter Island. In: Burkhard Vogt, Annette Kühlem, Hans-Rudolf Bork, and Andreas Mieth (eds.), Proceedings of the 9th International Conference on Easter Island and the Pacific – Cultural and Environmental Dynamics, Berlin June 2015. Wiesbaden: Reichert Verlag. (Forschungen zur Archäologie Außereuropäischer Kulturen Vol. 17)

Lavachery, Henri

- 1939 Les pétroglyphes de l'Île de Pâques. 2 vols. Antwerp: De Sikkel.

Lee, Georgia

- 2004 Rapa Nui's Sea Creatures. *Rapa Nui Journal* 18(1): 31-38.

Macri, Martha J.

1996 Rongorongo of Easter Island. In: Peter T. Daniels, and William Bright (eds.), *The World's Writing Systems*; pp. 183-188. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

McCall, Grant

1981 Rapanui: Tradition and Survival on Easter Island. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press.

Métraux, Alfred

1940 Ethnology of Easter Island. Honolulu: Bishop Museum Press. (Bernice P. Bishop Museum Bulletin 160)

1957 Easter Island: A Stone-Age Civilization of the Pacific. London: Andre Deutsch Limited.

Moerenhout, J. A.

1837 Voyages aux îles du Grand Océan. Paris: Arthus Bertrand.

Oliver, Douglas

2002 Polynesia in Early Historic Times. Honolulu: The Bess Press Inc.

Pozdniakov, Konstantin

1996 Les bases du déchiffrement de l'écriture de l'île de Pâques. *Journal de la Société des Océanistes* 103(2): 289-303.

Roussel, Hippolyte

1908 Vocabulaire de la langue de l'Île-de-Pâques ou Rapanui. *Le Muséon* 27: 159-254.

Routledge, Katharine (Scoresby)

- 1914-1915 Unpublished field notes. In: Papers of Katherine Scoresby Routledge, relating chiefly to Easter Island, 1911-1923. Royal Geographical Society, London. Microfilm at the Pacific Manuscripts Bureau, Australian National University, Canberra (PMB 531, Reels 1-4).
- 1919 The Mystery of Easter Island. The Story of an Expedition. London: Hazell, Watson and Viney.

Steiner, Hartwig-E.

- 2008 Die Jungfrauen-Höhle auf der Osterinsel Ana O Keke' auf Poike / Rapa Nui, Polynesien. *Almogaren* 39: 253-320.
- 2014 Zeichen des Vogelmann-Kultes der Osterinsel in den Höhlen auf Motu Nui / Polynesien. *Almogaren* 44/45: 269-398.

Stolpe, H.

- 1899 Über die Tätowirung der Oster-Insulaner. *Abhandlungen und Berichte des Königlichen Zoologischen und Anthropologisch-Ethnographischen Museums zu Dresden* 8. (Festschrift Nr. 6)

Thomson, William J.

- 1891 Te Pito te Henua, or Easter Island. In: Report of the United States National Museum for the Year Ending June 30, 1889; pp. 447-552. Washington, DC: Smithsonian Institution. (Annual Reports of the Smithsonian Institution for 1889)

Tregear, Edward

- 1891 The Maori-Polynesian Comparative Dictionary. Wellington: Lyon and Blair.

Sources of illustrations

Except where noted, illustrations are from the transcriptions of Barthel (1958). Tablet sides are indicated by Barthel as “r” (recto) and “v” (verso) or – when the reading order is uncertain – as “a” and “b”. Corrected transcriptions are marked by an asterisk.

1:adapted from Steiner 2008:311 (fig. 17); 2a:Hv8; b:Hv9; c:Aa2; d:Aa4; e:Hr5; f:Br9; 3a:Ca1; b:Ra6; 4:adapted from Steiner 2014:342 (fig. 34); 5a:Hv10; b:Pv11; c:Pv6; d:Hv4; 6a:I1; b:Hr7; c:Aa8; 7a:Hv12; b:Aa4; c:Bv2; d:Aa1; 9a:Hv11; b:Ab1; 8a:Aa1; b:Hv7; c:Ab7; d:Aa5; e:Pv7; f:Hv6; 10a:Ca2; b:Ab7; c:Steiner 2008:311, fig. 17 (detail); d:Ev8; e:Ab8; 11: photo and drawing by the author; 12a:Pv9; b:Ev7; c:I9; d:Ca2; 13a:Qv2; b:Hr11; 14a:Qv8; b:Hv5; c:Sb6; d:I11; 15a:Stolpe 1899:11, fig. 14 (detail); b:Lavachery 1939, vol.2, fig. 13bis (details); 16a:Gv1; b:Br7; c:Er4; d:Aa1; 17a:Ab6; b:Er1; c:Ca8; 18a:Bv3; b:Hv10; c:Bv8 (detail); 19a:Ab6; b:Qr3; 20a:Hv11; b:Aa4; c:Ev6; d:Hv3; 21:Hr4; 22a:Qr6; b:Gv6; c:Pr4; d:Hr5; 23:Cb7; 24a:Aa6; b:Br8; c:I11; d:Hv11; 25a:Br7; b:Hv11; c:Aa4; d:Br5; 26:Bv9; 27a:Ra2; b:Ev5; c:Ca2*; 28a:Aa5; b:Qv7*; c:Hv10; 29a:Bv3; b:Br9; 30a:Hr2; b:Pr2*; 31a:Ab1; b:Ab1*; 32a:Hr4; b:Ra4; c:Ab5; d:Db5*; 33a:Ab1*; b:Ab1; 34a:Pr4; b:Hr4; 35a:Aa6; b:Hv11; 36a:Pr10; b:Qv1; 37a:Hv4; b:Ab5; 38a:Aa3; b:Ab5; 39a:Er3; b:Gr1-2; 40:Er2; 41:Hv11; 42: Er2; 43:Ab2; 44: Steiner 2008:311, fig. 17 (detail); 45a:Hv10; b:Ev3; 46a:Cb12; b:Rb6; 47a:Aa2; b:Pv5; c:Ab5; 48a:Aa8*; b:Ab1; c:Ab1; d:I9; 49a:Gv2; b:I9; 50:Db4; 51:Cb3*; 52a:Hv7; b:Pv9; 53:Ab8; 54a:Bv1; b:Qr1; 55a:Ab1*; b:Ab1; 56a:Er6; b:Aa8; c:Pv9; d:Hv8; e:Bv11; 57a:Hv2; b:Ab3; 58a:I2*; b:Hr5; c:Gv6; 59a:Rb4; b:Aa1; c:T4; d:T10; e:Aa2; f:I14; g:Gv3; h:Gv3; 60a:I8; b:I10; c:I1; 61a:I2*; b:I6; c:I3; 62a:Er2; b:Ca2; 63:Ra4*; 64a:Ev8; b:Qv1; 65a:I2; b:I3; c:I1; d:I14; e:I2; f:Ab4; 66a:Pr5; b:Hr5; c:Aa1; d:Pr3; 67:Aa2; 68a:I8; b:I5; c:Hv1; d:Gr2*; e:Hv8; f:Pv9*; 69a:Cb12; b:Qv3; c:I13; 70:Gv6; 71a:Gr2*; b:Gv4; 72:Br3; 73:Er6; 74:Aa1; 75a:Aa1; b:Sa4; 76a:Sa5; b:I9; 77a:Sa1*; b:Pv5;

78a:I10; b:I14; c:I5; d:I1; 79:I12; 80a:Hv9; b:I6*; 81a:Hv12; b:I6*; 82:Ra6; 83a:Hr3; b:Hr3;
84a:Pr5*; b:Hr5; 85a:Ab8*; b:Gv3; 86:Ra4*